

CESSDA ERIC Agenda 21-24, Tasks 21-22

Widening of CESSDA European Coverage

D4 Strategy for development of the CESSDA Newsletter

Document info

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	31/05/2022
Actual Submission Date	12/09/2022
Type	Report
Approval Status	Approved by Working Group Leader Jindrich Krejci
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.16
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.5554451

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and CESSDA ERIC is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Version history

Version	Date	Comment	Revised by
0.1	2021-08-10	First draft	Rodney Appleyard
0.2	2022-03-28	Second draft	Sharmila Peake
0.3	2022-04-22	Version for peer-review	Sharmila Peake
0.4	2022-08-05	Update after peer review	Sharmila Peake
1.0	2022-09-11	Version to submit	Rodney Appleyard

Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact information
The UK Data Service	Rodney Appleyard	rodney.appleyard@essex.ac.uk
The UK Data Service	Sharmila Peake	sharmila.peake@essex.ac.uk
SND	Iris Alfredsson	iris.alfredsson@snd.gu.se
CESSDA MO	Eleanor Smith	eleanor.smith@cessda.eu

Peer-review

Organisation	Name	Contact information
GESIS	Kristi Winters	kristi.winters@gesis.org
The UK Data Service	Gemma Hakins	ghakins@essex.ac.uk

Contents

Executive Summary	3
Abbreviations and Acronyms	4
Background of the newsletter	5
Newsletter statistics	6
Reader feedback	10
CESSDA Working Group Leaders and MO feedback	11
Editorial team response to newsletter statistics, reader and stakeholder feedback	13
Strategic recommendations from the editorial team	14

Executive Summary

The CESSDA Widening and Outreach strategy was the impetus behind the relaunch of the CESSDA newsletter. The newsletter was intended to support and encourage the regular sharing of news, resources, funding, and training opportunities amongst the CESSDA members and partners.

As it stands, the CESSDA newsletter is a very strong example of the success of the CESSDA project. The current collaborative approach takes advantage of communications expertise of a team of professionals at the UK Data Service and the Senior Communication Officer at CESSDA MO and the academic insight into data management at the Swedish National Data Archive (SND), who together research, write, edit and project manage the newsletter. It also relies on the input of partners across the CESSDA network to generate content ideas relevant to the subscribers (now over 800), who consist of researchers and social science experts.

The newsletter contains the following regular features:

- In the Spotlight – the main news feature, typically an interview or highlighting a major event or project
- News – other, second-tier news items
- Funding and international collaboration – opportunities for researchers
- Events, Training, Resources and Vacancies.

This document will further outline the initial strategy behind the launch of the newsletter, highlight its performance statistics, explore feedback sourced from the subscription base and CESSDA working group and MO staff, before concluding with recommendations for ongoing working practice, improvements, and strategy from the editorial team.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ADP	The Slovenian Social Science Data Archives
CDC	CESSDA Data Catalogue
CESSDA MO	CESSDA Main Office
CTR	Click-through Rate
FORS	Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences
SND	Swedish National Data Service
SPs	Service Providers

1. Background of the newsletter

During early 2020 plans to further implement the CESSDA mentorship scheme, as part of the CESSDA Widening and Outreach strategy, were in motion. However, as the COVID-19 pandemic developed during the early months of 2020, it became apparent that the restrictions imposed on normal working life would curtail the planned mentor activities. The mentorship team (ADP, FORS, SND) discussed how to proceed with providing a much needed exchange of information on resources, funding and training opportunities between CESSDA partners and beyond. A fortnightly newsletter was piloted in May 2020.

The newsletter was intended to include more information than the information shared through ordinary CESSDA communication channels and function as a more regular output, since only three CESSDA newsletters were published previously between December 2018 and November 2019. A more regularly published events bulletin was incorporated into the newsletter.

The news, events and resources included in the newsletter were selected for the target audience of data service professionals as well as data service users, namely researchers and students in social sciences. Merging the mailing lists of the previous version of the newsletter and the events bulletin for data professionals established a subscription base of 448.

In total, from June 2020 to February 2021 the editors sent 18 newsletters. The newsletter was compiled in a Google document and then sent out as a PDF via ordinary email, so no readership statistics could be ascertained.

By February 2021, the immediate objectives of the newsletter pilot scheme had been successfully achieved. The newsletter had answered its brief, as outlined by the aims of the CESSDA Widening and Outreach strategy. The project itself was evidence of a successful collaboration, primarily between SND, ADP and FORS, with other SPs contributing news and events to an extent. Furthermore, an irregular news update had been replaced with a regular and reliable communication, which contained valuable information for data professionals.

The team carried out an assessment of the impact of the newsletter in February 2021, and identified the main strategy challenges for the future:

1. to deepen engagement with CESSDA SPs and partners to share their news, and;
2. to increase the number of recipients.

Even though data service professionals had been widely invited to subscribe to the newsletter, it was noted that target readers within communications and IT teams at SPs had not yet signed up. These staff were identified as key partners to share their institutions' news, publications, and events.

In order to meet these strategic goals, the editors reflected on how to bring the newsletter to the next level. The editors and the CESSDA Senior Communication Officer decided to move the newsletter to MailerLite, a dedicated tool for sending professional newsletters. This tool also facilitated the management of subscriptions and enabled statistical analysis of the newsletter.

A new editorial team was established in the CESSDA work plan 2021-2022, and it was decided that the review of the newsletter (in terms of content and form) as well as the strategic challenges should be tackled by the new team.

The transition between the 2020 team and the 2021-2022 team (SND, UK Data Service and CESSDA MO) was made progressively. The newsletter's concept and the new version were discussed by the two teams in December and January. The CESSDA Newsletter 2.0 was sent for the first time in March 2021 by the new team. In July 2021 a small change to the template layout was A/B tested, in an effort to reduce scroll time through the newsletter sections on Events, Training, Resources and Vacancies. The adjusted layout received a CTR of 16.7% compared to the old layout receiving a CTR of 11.5%, so the new layout was adopted.

The new editorial team conducted a User Survey which ran from July 2021 to March 2022, which involved asking users to submit their thoughts about the newsletter. Analysis of the survey answers is included in the section on Reader Feedback and informs the plans and recommendations on how to make the newsletter even more effective in the future.

2. Newsletter statistics

(See table and graphs overleaf)

Table 1 covers issues from 1 March 2021 to 9 May 2022. It shows the increase in subscriber numbers across this period, from 448 to 702. It includes details of the newsletter email subject titles. To reflect best practice, headline content information from "In the Spotlight" was included in the subject line from 30 April onwards, but this did not make much difference to open rates, which remain consistently strong at around 40%. This is much higher than usual newsletters and is a sign of significant success. CTR usually lies between

10-20%. The number of weekly unsubscribes is low, far outstripped by new subscribers. The table includes the most popular link, which is typically located within "In the Spotlight".

Figures 1 and 2 show subscriber levels, open rate and click through rate in some more detail. Figure 1 depicts the exponential subscriber growth and a steady open rate. Figure 2 shows more clearly that the open rate is increasing, climbing from around 200 to 300 across the period, but the CTR is not increasing at the same rate, and typically fluctuates.

Picture 1. Issue titles, top links and reader statistics, covering 1 March 21 to 9 May 2022. Source: MailerLite, CESSDA ERIC.

Issue no	Date	No of recipients	Subject line	Number of opens	Opens by percentage	Unopened emails	Clicks	Unsubscribes	Top link*
4	01-Mar-21	448	CESSDA Newsletter - 1 March 2021/Issue 4	216	49.32%		21.20%		Training section - Open Badge Ecosystem for the Recognition of Skills in Research Data Management and Sharing (free 3-week course)
5	15-Mar-21	457	CESSDA Newsletter - 15 March 2021/Issue 5	212	47.43%		18.57%		2 Spotlight section - A Day in the life of a Data Archivist (01)
6	29-Mar-21	461	CESSDA Newsletter - 29 March 2021/Issue 6	210	46.56%		19.96%		1 Training section - Webinar: FAIR Data: From principles to best practices
7	16-Apr-21	462	CESSDA Newsletter - 16 April 2021/Issue 7	212	47.01%		19.29%		1 Spotlight section - What is metadata and how do I document my data?
8	30-Apr-21	461	CESSDA Newsletter - Main Feature - First Europe-wide survey in to well-being of children	198	43.33%	260	16.19%		0 Spotlight section - COORDINATE — Researchers to develop first ever Europe-wide survey to track children's wellbeing
9	14-May-21	465	CESSDA Newsletter - Learn more about Responsible Open Science	201	43.60%	260	18.87%		2 Spotlight section - Responsible Open Science network
10	28-May-21	464	CESSDA Newsletter - EOSC Future's new strategic vision	202	44.89%	248	17.56%		0 Spotlight section - EOSC Future strategic vision
11	11-Jun-21	469	CESSDA Newsletter - Main Feature - CESSDA behavioural data for COVID-19 research	204	44.84%	251	15.16%		1 Spotlight section - CESSDA behavioural data for COVID-19 research
12	25-Jun-21	470	CESSDA Newsletter - Main Feature - Ten questions to Jan Dalsten Sørensen, Danish National Archives	172	37.72%	284	12.72%		0 Spotlight section - Ten questions...
13	09-Jul-21	460	CESSDA Newsletter - Ten Questions to Mercè Crosas - Plus register for SSHOC Workshops today.	155	35.39%	283	13.70%		1 Spotlight section - Ten questions..
14	20-Aug-21	463	CESSDA Newsletter - In the Spotlight this week; a new Dataverse translation app...	195	42.58%	263	18.56%		2 News section - UK Data Service new website
15	06-Sep-21	466	CESSDA Newsletter - Podcast on cross-disciplinary research on COVID-19	195	42.58%	263	21.40%		0 Spotlight section - CESSDA podcast on shared datasets
16	20-Sep-21	468	CESSDA Newsletter - CESSDA Roadshow registrations open	161	36.34%	282	9.71%		0 Spotlight section - CESSDA Roadshow Registrations
17	04-Oct-21	469	CESSDA Newsletter - Sign up to our CESSDA Roadshow on Migration	178	38.36%	286	14.44%		0 Training section - UK Data Service how to anonymise data
18	18-Oct-21	471	CESSDA Newsletter - Last stops on the CESSDA Roadshow: 21 & 28 October!	174	37.34%	292	12.02%		1 News section - CESSDA contributing EOSC
19	01-Nov-21	533	CESSDA Newsletter - CESSDA supports EU Science through the European Open Science Cloud	219	41.79%	305	15.27%		1 Spotlight section - CESSDA contributing to EOSC
20	15-Nov-21	564	CESSDA Newsletter - CESSDA is hiring a new Director!	221	39.61%	337	13.44%		1 Spotlight section - CESSDA to get a new director
21	13-Dec-21	661	CESSDA Newsletter - In the Spotlight: ten questions to Ron Dekker	279	42.79%	382	14.42%		3 Spotlight section - Ten questions...
1	17-Jan-22	668	CESSDA Newsletter - How should we share research data?	287	43.55%	381	15.02%		1 Spotlight section - How should we share research data?
2	14-Feb-22	673	CESSDA Newsletter - Launch of the SSH Open Marketplace	290	43.61%	383	14.59%		1 Spotlight section - Launch of the SSH Open Marketplace
3	14-Mar-22	683	CESSDA Newsletter - Dr Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch appointed as the new CESSDA Director	288	42.67%	395	13.19%		1 Spotlight section - Dr Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch etc...
Special	28-Mar-22	690	CESSDA Newsletter - Special issue on SSHOC - register for the final conference now	289	42.31%	401	8.64%		1 Spotlight section - Last chance to register for final conference now
4	11-Apr-22	689	CESSDA Newsletter - An MOU to bolster cloud services for the SSH	279	40.85%	410	11.71%		2 Spotlight section - MOU bolster to cloud services
5	09-May-22	702	CESSDA Newsletter - SSHOC's video game to improve data management knowledge	289	41.58%	413	15.25%		1 Spotlight section - SSHOC video game

* discounting "View in web browser" button

Figure 1: CESSDA newsletter: Recipients and open rate. Source: Mailerlite, CESSDA ERIC.

Figure 2: Subscribers, open rates and click through. Source: Mailerlite, CESSDA ERIC.

3. Reader feedback

Newsletter subscribers have had the opportunity to respond to a feedback survey; the link featured in every issue from July 2021 through to March 2022, the CESSDA Senior Communication Officer regularly promoted it via Twitter and the survey was flagged at the regular monthly comms call on several occasions.

As identified by the reader survey and might be predicted, the audience sample primarily consists of professionals within the social science research community. Research support staff (such as librarians, data specialists) and social scientists make up the majority of the audience sample, with one respondent in a ministerial role and three in communications.

The respondent level was lower than hoped, so a short invitation for feedback was sent out to the subscriber list on 1 December 2021. There have now been eighteen responses in total, which was much better. The responses were discursive and useful.

In brief, the response was very positive. The feedback included comments such as:

"It has a lot of interesting announcements and useful links. It is written in excellent English. It often announces events before my national service does."

"It gathers all types of news into an easily browsable format."

"Very esthetic [sic], neat, easy to skim over, exhaustive (complete)"

Table 1: Summary of feedback from the recipient survey. Source: CESSDA Newsletter Survey, Collected July 2021 to March 2022, N=18.

Survey question	Respondent feedback
What do you like most about the CESSDA newsletter?	Respondents were very positive about the news, training and events content in the newsletter. Events appear to be the most popular section, with training and resources not far behind.
In your opinion, how do you think the new newsletter compares to the previous CESSDA newsletters?	Several respondents had not received the older version of the newsletter, but those that had strongly preferred the new version, in terms of both content and design. News content was praised as more "relevant".
What kind of information would you like to see more of in future newsletters?	Five respondents request more news from service providers and more on CESSDA events.

	One respondent mentioned highlighting specific datasets, another wanted more profiles and recommended reading (which, it could be argued, is covered by the Resources section, but perhaps this needs to be made more explicit).
What kind of information would you prefer to see less of?	Responses to this were generally ambivalent, the audience sample were quite positive about the current content. One reader would like to see fewer events listed, another suggests removing the "In the Spotlight" section.
Newsletter length and frequency	Over 80% of the respondents thought the newsletter length was just right. Most of the audience sample would be happy to see the newsletter once a month (although with caveats).
Do you think the CESSDA Newsletter has the potential to benefit your organisation by including your latest news items, events happening in your country and job vacancies available at your organisation, etc.?	There is a fairly positive reaction to this statement. However, one responder points out that "not all news or events [from their home SPs] are relevant to the wider CESSDA audience" while another feels that their SP's own channels provide satisfactory publication of news from their territory.
What is the best way for you to send us new content for the newsletter?	Direct mail or via Basecamp
Would you like us to arrange a set date each month for you to send us a digital update on content for inclusion in future newsletters?	Respondents appreciate a reminder.

4. CESSDA Working Group Leaders and MO feedback

Opinions on the newsletter from Working Group Leaders and MO management staff at CESSDA had been gathered via personalised emails. A small number of CESSDA Working Group Leaders and MO staff responded to the personalised emails; their responses are here termed as being from Respondents A, B, C, D and E. A wide range of views were expressed.

Respondent A offered useful views of the newsletter. In the respondent's opinion it was not well known and needed further promotion. The respondent also felt the content could be more visually appealing and include more engaging content. Respondent A provided an

example of the CERIC-ERIC newsletter¹, which the respondent liked in terms of both content and design. Respondent A suggested that the editorial team should consult in the future with CESSDA partner TRUST-IT on the design of the email. It was discovered later that TRUST-IT was, in fact, involved in the design process from the outset. Respondent A felt that the newsletter could be improved by more strategic planning and communication with CESSDA Working Group leaders and SP project contacts with monthly updates on the current projects.

Respondent B liked the “In the Spotlight” feature and felt more could be done to feature Service Providers. The respondent also disliked the use of narrow columns, but felt there was too much scrolling through the content (the columns were introduced as a layout change in July 2021 to reduce the amount of scrolling and A/B tested). Additionally, they felt that news items should be shortened and the primary focus of the newsletter should be on CESSDA activities and project outcomes. Finally, the respondent suggested highlighting the latest datasets added to the CESSDA catalogue.

Respondent C suggested that newsletters could be more thematic in approach and be more appealing to the spectrum of the readership. Respondent C suggested that a workflow should be established to monitor new resources, vacancies, events, and project outputs (public outputs from CESSDA work plans and from CESSDA-involved projects). There is a workflow already in place that does this, which will be shared in more detail with the respondents in the future, to consult over, in case it could be improved further.

Respondent C also suggested that the newsletter needs more promotion in order to give a better return on investment (in terms of time and resources) and suggested that including more news relating to SPs and named employees would see the newsletter being widely promoted through SP and personal channels (social media or otherwise). On the subject of further promotion, Respondent D flagged up the opportunity to achieve greater visibility via LinkedIn.

Additionally, respondent D suggested that with the inclusion of more content on the CESSDA website, such as an area for blogs, would mean the content of the newsletter could be broadened. Respondent D echoed the view that more content related to projects where CESSDA is a long-term partner should be included.

Respondent E noted that the newsletter contains a range of highly relevant content, including news from SPs, training, and job opportunities, plus CESSDA developments. The

¹ CERIC ERIC Newsletter: <https://mailchi.mp/ae975f4e007b/ceric-newsletter-27-january-2022>

respondent praised the newsletter as a comprehensible and visually appealing source of important information. Respondent E went on to point out that the newsletter content generally reflected and was determined by news from the workflow of CESSDA projects, so there was no need to develop a particular strategy to uphold this. The respondent also said that the promotion of events and training will be possible in the future through further discussion between the CESSDA newsletter editorial team and the SP contacts. This could involve the editorial team helping the SPs to forward plan the sharing of their content either directly with the editorial team or via their own websites and social media channels.

5. Editorial team response to newsletter statistics, reader and stakeholder feedback

The February 2021 review identified two strategic challenges: increasing subscriptions and deepening engagement with SPs. Analysis of the statistical performance of the newsletter and feedback received offers valuable insight into how far these objectives have been achieved.

Increased subscriptions

There is clearly a growing awareness of the CESSDA newsletter. The increased subscriber numbers speak for themselves, having grown from 448 in March 2021 to the current number of over 800 in August 2022. The biggest spike was due to the excellent promotional work carried out by the communication team at CESSDA MO during the CESSDA Roadshow series, generating hundreds of new sign-ups. New subscribers remain and the unsubscribe rate is low. The sample of readers who responded to the feedback survey voiced a strong appreciation for the mix of news, training and events and the quality of content and writing, which could possibly account for the low unsubscribe rate. The Open Rate has also remained steady and the CTR figures are good too. However, driving up opens and CTR further, to enhance engagement, is to be prioritised.

Engagement with SPs

The editorial team has been proactive in seeking engagement with the wider SP network, encouraging input and feedback via personalised emails and during regular communications calls arranged by CESSDA MO. However, the editorial team would welcome even more engagement with senior staff at CESSDA and SPs to improve the content even further in the future.

The feedback offered via the survey offers a broadly positive view of the newsletter in its current form, with those readers stating that they value the design and content.

A number of the CESSDA MO stakeholders who responded to requests for feedback also believe there should be greater engagement with the editorial team about bigger long-term CESSDA projects. This refinement of the newsletter can be achieved with more planning and input between the CESSDA editorial team, the key CESSDA stakeholders and working group leaders.

6. Strategic recommendations from the editorial team

The CESSDA newsletter is now in a position to build further on the strategic goals outlined by the February 2021 review. From September 2022, the following strategic goals could be adopted:

1. Maintain the CESSDA newsletter as a collaborative project
2. Continue regular promotion of news, events and opportunities
3. Further development of links with wider CESSDA partners and project contacts
4. Promotion of the newsletter as a benefit of CESSDA membership
5. Aim to increase subscription, CTR and open rates

In order to meet these goals, the editorial team suggests reviewing the following:

Frequency

Having moved from fortnightly to monthly publication, the team believes publishing once a month is more appropriate due to the available resources in terms of available time and personnel at the UK Data Service, SND and CESSDA MO.

Monthly publication provides more time to source richer and original content and could mean in time the newsletter can become even more engaging for users, leading to further improvements to the subscription, CTR and open rates. Furthermore, in terms of frequency, most of the audience sample who responded to the survey would be happy to see the newsletter once a month. The team has not found that a monthly newsletter means that training or other events were missed out. The newsletter would remain a regular source of information on data archive news, events and opportunities.

Overall content

While the newsletter length should remain as it is, having been praised as concise and digestible, the team suggests there are two possible options for developing content strategy.

Both options would support the goals of further development of links with wider CESSDA partners and project contacts, continue regular promotion of news, events and opportunities and increase subscription, CTR and open rates.

Option 1; having reduced to monthly publication, keep the content and look of the newsletter more or less as it is. It has proved popular with the general readership and taken on a significant increase in subscription with a low unsubscribe rate. The editorial team will allow for some more time to research, plan and edit more content that reflects CESSDA project workflows, while also continuing to publish content that arises organically from current and topical subjects relevant to the audience when the newsletter is published.

Option 2; focus the monthly edition around delivery of more strategically aligned content. Plan issues around key CESSDA projects and themes, balancing between data content and data architecture to appeal to the whole audience. However, the execution of a newsletter that tracks key CESSDA internal and external projects more closely will require a much closer working relationship with the CESSDA Working Group, which could be achieved through a new monthly meeting with the project leads.

Engagement with SPs and Working Group leaders

With the aim of maintaining the newsletter as a collaborative project, as discussed above, whatever the strategy for the future of the newsletter project, it will rely on enhanced communication with SPs, MO project staff, and Working Group leaders. The newsletter team would welcome the opportunity to talk more regularly with stakeholders at SPs and at CESSDA MO when it comes to creating new content. The CESSDA editorial team would be keen to speak with the management at CESSDA MO and SPs about how we can put together a joint vision for the future content of the newsletter over the next year. If a monthly call is too much for regular meetings, the editorial team would also welcome quarterly meetings with the stakeholders, to bring this vision to life. This kind of communicative effort would serve the strategic objective of further development of links with wider CESSDA partners and project contacts.

Align with CESSDA website

The look and feel of the newsletter should be updated to reflect the new website, launched in June 2022. This is important for branding and visibility and also an opportunity to point to up-to-date content pages at cessda.eu (e.g. event listings and news items, etc.).

In all cases, it would be sensible to create new CESSDA web pages that the editorial can link to, so they spend minimal time on reproducing listings within the newsletter and spend more

editorial time on strategic content instead. This would support the continuance of regular promotion of news, events and opportunities.

Promotion and visibility

Continue promotional efforts of the newsletter at all CESSDA internal and external events (e.g. CESSDA Comms calls, WG meetings, project meetings, etc.), with emphasis on it being a community resource and a unique benefit of CESSDA membership. MO project and CESSDA pillar contacts should be encouraged to flag the newsletter within their own channels. It is to be hoped that this will increase subscription rates, building links across the CESSDA network. LinkedIn was mentioned by one of the CESSDA MO respondents as a valuable platform for promotion. Publishing on LinkedIn could see an increase in subscription rates. However, regular promotion on LinkedIn in addition to the ongoing promotion already happening on Twitter would require further communication resources at CESSDA MO.

The concentrated effort to drive up subscription rates during the CESSDA Roadshow series yielded excellent results. The best results will be achieved by all CESSDA stakeholders working together even more closely with the CESSDA editorial team to enhance our communication efforts, in the spirit of "I am, we are CESSDA". The editorial team is looking forward to speaking further with all involved about how we can make this happen in the future.